

Effects of Breakfast Strategies on 5-km Running Performance: A Pilot Study

Short title: Breakfast and 5-km Performance

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Abstract

This exploratory pilot study investigated whether different pre-exercise breakfast strategies influence running speed during a 5-km run performed at a fixed relative heart rate in recreational runners. Four participants completed three experimental conditions in a within-subject crossover design, with each condition performed twice, resulting in a total of 24 trials. The conditions included (A) fasted running, (B) ingestion of rapidly available carbohydrates in the form of a banana consumed 10 minutes before exercise, and (C) consumption of a mixed breakfast consisting of oats and banana 60 minutes before exercise. All runs were conducted on the same outdoor 5-km course to ensure environmental consistency. Exercise intensity was standardized at 75–80% of each participant's individual maximal heart rate. Within-subject differences in running speed were analyzed under comparable cardiovascular load. Results showed that all participants achieved higher running speeds following rapid carbohydrate intake compared with the fasted condition. In contrast, responses to the mixed breakfast condition were heterogeneous, with both improvements and reductions in running speed relative to the rapid carbohydrate condition. These preliminary findings suggest that ingestion of a small amount of rapidly available carbohydrates shortly before a 5-km run may enhance performance.

Keywords: pre-exercise nutrition, carbohydrate timing, fasted exercise, recreational running, heart rate-controlled exercise

Introduction

Breakfast is traditionally considered an important meal of the day; however, only about half of adults report eating breakfast regularly [1]. In recreational running, morning training sessions are frequently performed in a fasted state, and many runners assume that skipping breakfast has little impact on performance during short runs. From a sports nutrition perspective, carbohydrates play a central role in energy provision during exercise [2–4], whereas proteins and fats primarily serve structural and regulatory functions [5–8]. Micronutrients are essential for numerous physiological processes but do not directly contribute to acute energy supply [9]. Energy metabolism during running depends on exercise intensity, duration, and substrate availability [10,11]. In endurance exercise, muscle glycogen stores are a key determinant of performance [4,12], while heart rate is an established parameter for controlling and comparing exercise intensity [14,15]. Although the physiological mechanisms of fasted exercise and pre-exercise feeding are well described [16–18], data directly comparing different breakfast strategies before short-distance running are limited. Therefore, the aim of this exploratory pilot study was to investigate the effects of three practical breakfast strategies on 5-km running performance.

Methods

Participants

This exploratory within-subject crossover study included four healthy recreational runners (two women and two men; age range 17–48 years) with varying training volume and aerobic capacity. All participants were regularly engaged in running but were not competitive athletes. Each participant completed all experimental conditions twice, resulting in a total of 24 running trials (eight per condition). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to participation.

Measures

The primary outcome was running speed (min/km) achieved at a predefined relative heart rate. Heart rate was continuously monitored using a standardized smartwatch device. Individual maximal heart rate was defined as the highest value recorded by the smartwatch during training sessions within the previous six months. Subjective well-being and perceived performance were assessed after each run using standardized self-report questionnaires.

Procedures

Three experimental conditions were examined: (A) fasted running, (B) ingestion of rapidly available carbohydrates before running, and (C) consumption of a mixed breakfast.

In condition A, participants ran in a fasted state 15 minutes after waking, consuming only 200 mL of water. In condition B, participants ingested 1.5 g of banana per kilogram of body mass with 200 mL of water 10 minutes before running, providing rapidly available carbohydrates with good gastrointestinal tolerance [3] In condition C, participants consumed a mixed breakfast consisting of 1.25 g of oats and 1.0 g of banana per kilogram of body mass, along with 200 mL of water, 60 minutes before running to allow digestion and nutrient availability.

Nutritional intake in conditions B and C was adjusted to body mass. Fluid intake was standardized across all conditions. All runs were performed on the same outdoor 5-km course. Running intensity was controlled using heart rate monitoring and maintained within 75–80% of individual maximal heart rate. The mean heart rate of the first run was used as a reference for subsequent trials to ensure comparable cardiovascular load. To minimize potential confounding factors, participants were instructed to obtain at least eight hours of sleep prior to each trial, consume an evening meal before testing, perform runs at ambient temperatures below 25 °C, and refrain from participation if experiencing any relevant physical complaints [13].

Analysis

Within-subject differences in running speed were analyzed across conditions. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data. Mean differences in running speed between conditions were calculated and expressed in absolute and relative terms.

Results

Four recreational runners completed all trials, resulting in 24 runs. Baseline characteristics showed interindividual variability in age, aerobic capacity, and training volume (Table 1).

Variable	Median (range)
Sex (female/male)	2 / 2
Age, years	33 (17–48)
BMI, kg/m ²	22.7 (18.9–25.7)
Maximal heart rate, bpm	191 (178–203)
VO ₂ max, mL·kg ⁻¹ ·min ⁻¹	46 (40–52)
Weekly training volume, min	173 (120–270)

Across all breakfast conditions, the target heart rate range of 75–80% of maximal heart rate was maintained, with minimal variability (≤ 4 bpm). In the fasted condition (A), all participants achieved higher running speeds in the second trial, with differences ranging from 5 to 36 s/km. Mean heart rate in this condition ranged from 134 to 157 bpm. Following rapid carbohydrate intake (condition B), two participants showed higher running speeds and two showed lower running speeds compared with the fasted condition, while heart rate remained within the predefined range.

In the mixed breakfast condition (C), performance differed between trials, with three participants achieving higher running speeds in the first trial and one in the second. Given the stable heart rate across conditions, comparisons focused on running speed differences between conditions.

Compared with the fasted condition, all participants demonstrated higher running speeds following rapid carbohydrate intake, with differences ranging from 1.5% to 10.2%. In the mixed breakfast condition, three participants showed lower running speeds compared with condition B. Compared with the fasted condition, three participants achieved higher running speeds after the mixed breakfast, while one showed a lower running speed. Mean differences in running speed were $-0:23$ min/km (-5.8%) between conditions A and B, $+0:17$ min/km ($+4.0\%$) between B and C, and $-0:07$ min/km (-2.1%) between A and C, with interindividual variability (Table 2).

Comparison	Mean difference (min/km)	Percent difference (%)	SD (min/km)
A vs. B	-0:23	-5.8	0:15
B vs. C	+0:17	+4.0	0:14
A vs. C	-0:07	-2.1	0:24
A = fasted condition; B = rapid carbohydrate intake; C = mixed breakfast			

Subjective ratings showed the highest scores for perceived well-being during rapid carbohydrate intake (mean 8.1/10), while lower scores were reported in the fasted and mixed breakfast conditions. Self-perceived performance was most frequently rated as “as usual” in condition B, whereas negative ratings were more frequent in the fasted condition.

Discussion

This exploratory study demonstrated pronounced interindividual differences in running speed despite a controlled cardiovascular load of 75–80% of maximal heart rate. These differences may be attributable to variations in age, sex, and aerobic capacity, consistent with established declines in performance with age and higher cardiorespiratory capacity in men compared with women [20,21]. The observed performance ranking appeared to align with baseline physiological characteristics, supporting the validity of the heart rate–controlled design. An improvement in running speed during the second trial of the fasted condition was observed in all participants, which may reflect familiarization with fasted running and adaptation to heart rate control during the initial exposure. In contrast, no consistent pattern emerged between repeated trials in the carbohydrate and mixed breakfast conditions, suggesting a potential influence of day-to-day variability, recovery status, or environmental factors. Across conditions, rapid carbohydrate intake was associated with higher running speeds compared with fasted running, with a mean improvement of 5.8%, suggesting a consistent performance benefit. This finding is in line with the faster availability of carbohydrates for ATP production compared with fat oxidation during moderate-intensity exercise. Performance following the mixed breakfast was inferior to the rapid carbohydrate condition, contrary to the initial hypothesis. This may be explained by delayed gastric emptying and prolonged insulin release after a larger meal rich in complex carbohydrates, potentially leading to transient reductions in blood glucose availability at exercise onset [8]. In contrast, carbohydrate ingestion shortly before exercise may coincide with catecholamine-mediated modulation of insulin secretion and enhanced hepatic glucose output, supporting stable glucose availability during running.

Given the short duration of the 5-km run, glycogen replenishment is unlikely to be a primary limiting factor, whereas timing of carbohydrate availability may be more relevant. Consistent with this, mixed breakfast intake resulted in slightly better performance than fasted running but with substantial interindividual variability, suggesting heterogeneous metabolic responses to pre-exercise feeding [4].

Subjective ratings mirrored the objective findings, with the highest perceived well-being and most favorable self-assessment of performance reported after rapid carbohydrate intake, while fasted running was rated least favorably. Potential confounders include ambient temperature, hydration status, daily physiological variability, and changes in training volume during the study period [7,13]. However, the repeated-measures design and controlled conditions may have reduced their overall impact, supporting the robustness of the observed trends.

Conclusion

Breakfast consumption strategies may influence short-distance running performance in recreational runners. In this exploratory pilot study, ingestion of a small amount of rapidly available carbohydrates shortly before a 5-km run was associated with more favorable objective and subjective outcomes, whereas fasted running and consumption of a mixed breakfast appeared less advantageous. These findings suggest that during moderate-intensity exercise lasting less than 60 minutes, the timing and rapid availability of carbohydrates may be more relevant for performance than overall meal size or glycogen replenishment. However, substantial interindividual variability indicates that responses to pre-exercise nutrition are highly individual and influenced by physiological and metabolic factors. Due to the small sample size and exploratory design, the results should be interpreted cautiously. Larger, controlled studies with randomized protocols and varying exercise durations are needed to confirm these findings. Nevertheless, the present results provide preliminary evidence that low-volume carbohydrate intake shortly before short-distance running may represent a practical and well-tolerated strategy for recreational runners.

Ethics statement

All participants provided written informed consent prior to participation. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. The study involved non-invasive exercise testing in healthy recreational runners, and no medical or invasive procedures were performed. According to local institutional regulations, formal ethical approval was not required.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Summary Box

What is already known?

Carbohydrate availability influences endurance performance, and fasted exercise alters substrate utilization. Evidence comparing practical breakfast strategies before short-distance running is limited.

What does this study add?

Ingestion of rapidly available carbohydrates shortly before a 5-km run was associated with higher running speed at comparable cardiovascular load compared with fasted running, whereas responses to a mixed breakfast were heterogeneous.

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